

Mercuration of Coumarins.

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It appears that no attempt has hitherto been made to introduce mercury into coumarins, although mercury derivatives of almost all typical organic compounds have previously been prepared (see Whitmore, "Organic Compounds of Mercury," American Chemical Society Monograph). The present paper deals with the mercurated coumarins.

The most effective reagent previously employed in the mercuration of organic compounds was mercuric acetate and in some cases also mercuric chloride; but these reagents failed to mercurate coumarin in aqueous, alcoholic or acetic acid solution. When, however, the lactonic ring in the coumarin molecule is broken up and the masked hydroxyl group is brought to prominence, mercuration readily takes place either with (a) yellow mercuric oxide or with (b) mercuric acetate.

(a) Mercuration with Yellow Mercuric Oxide.

Monochloro- and dichloro-mercuricoumarins have been obtained in satisfactory yields by boiling a very dilute alkaline solution of coumarin with yellow mercuric oxide for three to four hours and then acidifying with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold in the same way as was done by White (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 2355) for mercurating the phthaleins. That the lactone ring with the ethylene linking remains unaffected is established by the observations (1) that their behaviour towards sodium carbonate and bicarbonate is exactly similar to coumarin itself, and (2) that cinnamic acid is not mercurated when similarly treated. These products are soluble in caustic alkalis and the original compounds are reprecipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold. It is therefore evident that the mercury enters the benzene nucleus, as in the case of phenol. (Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2154) in the *ortho* and *para* positions to the hydroxyl group so that the dimercury derivative is 6:8-dichloro-mercuricoumarin (I) and the mono-mercury derivative is probably 6-chloromercuricoumarin (II), as it has been generally observed in the case of mono-substituted coumarins that substitution occurs more

readily in the position 6 (*para*) than in the *ortho* position (cf. 6-nitro-coumarin, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2110; 6-aldehydocoumarin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2428; coumarin-6-sulphonic acid, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 488).

That mercury does not enter in position 7 is shown by the fact that 4:7-dimethylcoumarin also behaves similarly to coumarin and gives a dimercurichloride when treated in the same manner. It is interesting to observe that when the position 6 is occupied by negative substituents, no mercury compound is formed but geometrical inversion takes place to *ortho*-coumaric acid derivatives as described in another paper.

When freshly prepared and moist, the mono-mercurichloride of coumarin, unlike the dimercurichloride, is soluble in ammonia, the original compound being reprecipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold; but when perfectly dried, its solubility in ammonia disappears, though it readily dissolves in caustic alkalis.

By qualitative tests it is found that the hydroxycoumarins such as β -methylumbelliferone and β -methyldaphnetin are also mercurated by similar treatment with mercuric oxide which undergoes drastic reduction and it is not possible to obtain the products in a sufficiently pure condition for analysis, while 6-aminocoumarin is oxidised by this treatment with mercuric oxide.

(b) *Mercuration with Mercuric Acetate.*

Mercuration of coumarin with mercuric acetate takes place by dissolving coumarin in caustic soda, carefully neutralising the excess of alkali with dilute acetic acid in the cold and then adding mercuric acetate to the solution of the coumarinic acid, when a thick voluminous precipitate is thrown down. This precipitate, when dissolved in cold caustic alkalis and reprecipitated by acetic acid, is found to be a diacetoxymurcuric derivative of *o*-coumaric acid and not of coumarin, as is proved by its ready solubility in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence. When it is boiled with a large volume

of moderately dilute hydrochloric acid, a quantitative yield of *o*-coumaric acid melting at 207—209° is obtained. The identical diacetoxymercuri-*o*-coumaric acid is also obtained when *o*-coumaric acid is treated with yellow mercuric oxide in the manner already described. It is interesting to note that similar inversion with the help of mercuric acetate has been observed in other cases also described in another paper.

By similar treatment with mercuric acetate, the hydroxycoumarins such as β -methylumbelliferone and β -methyldaphnetin, are easily mercurated, diacetoxymercuri-derivatives being obtained, which are insoluble in sodium carbonate or bicarbonate solution. The compound from β -methylumbelliferone readily dissolves in cold caustic alkalis and is precipitated unchanged by dilute acetic acid which shows that the mercury atoms have entered the benzene nucleus to form 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6:8-diacetoxymercuricoumarins. The compound from β -methyldaphnetin on the other hand is readily decomposed even by cold caustic alkalis, a greyish precipitate of mercury oxides containing metallic mercury being formed, and the product obtained by the addition of acetic acid to the filtrate is free from mercury; hence it is inferred that, in this case, the mercury atoms are attached to the oxygen of the hydroxyl groups as was also observed by Neogi and Chatterjee in the case of certain phenols and phenol-ethers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 221).

When 6-aminocoumarin in dilute acetic acid solution is warmed to 60-70° with an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate for a few minutes, a crystalline acetoxy-mercuric derivative is thrown down. This compound is insoluble in acids and does not respond to the diazo test, which proves the absence of a free amino-group; hence it is evident that the mercury atom replaces the hydrogen in the amino-group and not in the benzene nucleus. This view is further supported by the fact that the beautiful colour of 6-aminocoumarin is completely destroyed as in the case of other derivatives of aminocoumarin in which the hydrogen of the amino-group is replaced by different groups (*cf.* Morgan and Micklethwait, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1230). Such *N*-mercuri-derivatives were also obtained from aromatic amines with mercuric chloride in the presence of sodium bicarbonate by Neogi and Chatterjee (*loc. cit.*).

All the mercury derivatives of coumarin (including those which are freely soluble in ammonia when moist but become insoluble when dry) acquire more or less deep colour (yellow to green when treated

with ammonia in the powdered condition, and these coloured products are all found by qualitative tests to contain nitrogen. It has also been noted that these mercury derivatives are readily soluble in pyridin and the original substances are not precipitated by pouring the pyridin solution into water; in the case of dichloromercuricoumarin, a fine crystalline additive compound with pyridin has been isolated.

The mercury in these compounds has been estimated as mercuric sulphide after oxidation with potassium permanganate and sulphuric acid, strictly following the method described by White (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Chloromercuricoumarin.—A solution of coumarin (10 g.) in 4 per cent. caustic soda solution (200 c.c.) is diluted with water (500 c.c.) and the solution is boiled with finely powdered yellow mercuric oxide (15 g.) for three to four hours. The yellow solution soon assumes a red colour and the yellow colour of the mercuric oxide changes to grey. The cold solution is then filtered and left in a tall cylinder overnight, when grey precipitates collect at the bottom. The supernatant solution is carefully decanted off, filtered two or three times through an ordinary filter paper and carefully acidified in the cold with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a thick voluminous (slightly reddish) precipitate is thrown down. The precipitate is filtered off, dissolved in ammonia, the ammoniacal solution is rapidly filtered at the pump and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold. The precipitate is filtered off, thoroughly washed with large volumes of cold water and finally with rectified spirit. It is then dried in a vacuum desiccator; almost colourless heavy powder decomposing at 178° (yield, 80%). It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone and insoluble in most of the organic solvents, dissolves in ammonia when moist, readily dissolves in caustic alkalis with a reddish-yellow colour. (Found: Hg, 51.8, 51.6; Cl, 8.8. $C_9H_5O_2ClHg$ requires Hg, 52.55; Cl, 9.3 per cent.).

6:8-Dichloromercuricoumarin.—Coumarin (10 g.) is dissolved in a 4% caustic soda solution (200 c.c.) and the solution, diluted with water (500 c.c.) is boiled (3-4 hours) with finely powdered yellow mercuric oxide (40 g.). The solution is filtered, left overnight in a tall cylinder as in the previous case to remove colloidal impurities and carefully acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold.

The precipitate is filtered, removed to a beaker and treated with ammonia when the monomeric-derivative goes into solution and the residue assumes a greenish-blue colour. The precipitate is rapidly filtered at the pump from the ammoniacal solution, pressed and thoroughly washed with cold water. It is then dried in a vacuum desiccator and the finely powdered solid washed with warm alcohol (yield, 70%). It is a colourless heavy powder, decomposing at 207°, very slightly soluble in alcohol and glacial acetic acid and almost insoluble in all other organic solvents; insoluble in ammonia, sodium carbonate and bicarbonate solutions but dissolves in warm caustic alkalis without any decomposition. (Found: Hg, 64.3; Cl, 10.82. $C_9H_4O_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 65.04; Cl, 11.5 per cent.).

This dichloromercuri-derivative is readily soluble in pyridin and on pouring the pyridin solution into water a compound is obtained which can be crystallised from a large volume of boiling alcohol. The crystals, thus obtained, are recrystallised from benzene, when colourless needles are obtained melting at 225°. (Found: Cl, 9.8; N, 2.3. $C_9H_4O_2Cl_2Hg_2 \cdot C_5H_5N$ requires Cl, 10.23; N, 2.02 per cent.).

4:7-Dimethyl-6:8-dichloromercuricoumarin.—4:7-Dimethylcoumarin (5 g.) is dissolved in caustic soda solution (10%, 50 c.c.) and the solution, diluted with water (400 c.c.) is boiled (3.4 hours) with yellow mercuric oxide (20 g.). The red solution, thus obtained, is filtered off, left overnight in a tall cylinder and the supernatant solution decanted off, filtered through ordinary filter paper and carefully acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold, when a curdy thick precipitate is obtained. This is filtered off, and thoroughly washed with cold water. It is then dried in a vacuum desiccator and the powdered solid boiled with alcohol. It is a reddish powder, sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid and insoluble in other solvents, insoluble in ammonia, sodium carbonate and bicarbonate solutions but soluble in warm caustic alkalis. (Found: Hg, 61.4; 61.7. $C_{11}H_8O_2Cl_2Hg_2$ requires Hg, 62.2 per cent.).

3:5-Diacetoxymercuricoumaric acid.—Coumarin (5 g.) is dissolved in caustic soda solution (5 g. in 50 c.c.) and the cold alkaline solution is carefully neutralised with dilute acetic acid from a burette using litmus as an indicator. Mercuric acetate (15 g. dissolved in 100 c.c. water) acidified with acetic acid, is then readily added from a burette and the solution stirred, when a voluminous precipitate is

thrown down. The solution is then left for about half an hour and filtered. The precipitate is washed with cold water, dissolved in cold dilute caustic potash solution and precipitated with dilute acetic acid. The precipitate is filtered off, washed with water, dried in a vacuum desiccator and crystallised from dilute acetic acid (yield, 60%). It forms colourless needle-shaped crystals, decomposing at 215°. It is readily soluble in glacial acetic acid, ammonia and cold alkalis and also in sodium bicarbonate with effervescence, sparingly in alcohol. A further quantity of the mercury derivative is also obtained from the filtrate on keeping. (Found: Hg, 58.1, 58.2. $C_{13}H_{12}O_7Hg_2$ requires Hg, 58.8 per cent.).

The diacetoxymercuri-*o*-coumaric acid (10 g.) is boiled with water (300 c.c.) containing 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, when it goes into solution. The solution is filtered hot and the filtrate on cooling gives needle-shaped crystals of *o*-coumaric acid, m.p. 207-209°. This on treatment with sulphuric acid gives coumarin (m.p. 69°).

The identical diacetoxymercuri-*o*-coumaric acid (decomposing at 215°) is also obtained when a solution of *o*-coumaric acid (5 g.) in caustic alkali solution (3 g. in 50 c.c.), diluted with water (400 c.c.) is boiled (3-4 hours) with an excess of yellow mercuric oxide (20 g.). The solution is then filtered and the mercury derivative is precipitated with dilute acetic acid, filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from dilute acetic acid. (Found: Hg, 58.4. $C_{13}H_{12}O_7Hg_2$ requires Hg, 58.8 per cent.).

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-6:8-diacetoxymercuricoumarin.—A cold solution of β -methylumbelliferone (5 g.) in hot caustic soda solution is carefully neutralised with acetic acid and a solution of mercuric acetate (15 g.) is rapidly added before the precipitation of β -methylumbelliferone begins and the solution left for half an hour. The dirty yellow precipitate, thus obtained, is filtered, washed with water and dissolved in cold dilute caustic potash solution and precipitated with dilute acetic acid. It is a dirty brown powder sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid and alcohol, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution but readily dissolves in cold alkalis without any decomposition. (Found: Hg, 56.8, 57.04. $C_{14}H_{12}O_7Hg_2$ requires Hg, 57.8 per cent.).

4-Methyl-7:8-diacetoxymercurioxy coumarin.—A cold solution of β -methyl-daphnetin (5 g.) in hot caustic soda solution is carefully neutralised with acetic acid and an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (15 g.) is rapidly added before β -methyl-daphnetin is precipitated and

the solution left for about half an hour. The brown precipitate is filtered, thoroughly washed with water, acidified with acetic acid and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The powdered solid is washed with boiling alcohol to remove β -methyldaphnetin. The substance is a brown powder, insoluble in all the organic solvents and is readily decomposed by cold sodium carbonate and alkali solutions. (Found: Hg, 55.8. $C_{14}H_{12}O_8Hg_2$ requires Hg, 56.5 per cent.).

6-Acetoxymercuriaminocoumarin.—A solution of 6-aminocoumarin (2 g.) in dilute acetic acid is treated with a solution of mercuric acetate (4 g.) in water acidified with acetic acid and the solution heated to 60-70° for two or three minutes, when shining crystals separate. These are filtered off, washed with cold water acidified with acetic acid and crystallised from dilute acetic acid. The colourless shining prismatic crystals insoluble in acids, did not respond to diazo-test. (Found: Hg, 48.8 ; N, 3.03. $C_{11}H_9O_4NHg$ requires Hg, 47.7 ; N, 3.34 per cent.).

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